

Taipei National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine

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Entry tags: shrines, Taiwan, Religious Group, State Religion, China, Chinese Religion, Religious Place, Shrine

In 1946, the Nationalist leadership began renovating the Taipei Shinto shrine into the National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine to house the displaced spirits of the national dead. Renovated and renamed the National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine in 1969, the structure served as the national altar of the Republic of China in exile. As the Martyrs' Shrine establishes the sacrifice of life as the highest mark of citizenship, necro-citizenship—posthumous membership in the national community—is reserved for Nationalist stalwarts and those whose loyalty can be similarly construed. The National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine is a fascinating example of how religion and state intersect in allegedly secular countries. The shrine originated from Sun Yat-sen's aspiration to commemorate the anti-imperial martyrs of the 1911 Republic and the Nationalist government's attempt to marshal political allegiance during the Japanese invasion in the 1930s–1940s. Throughout the Cold War era, the spring and autumn sacrifices performed by the heads of state and visits to the shrine by foreign dignitaries served to affirm the sovereignty of the Republic of China over the People's Republic of China. Even though the end of martial law in 1987 ushered in a new era marked by the Nationalist Party's loss of political hegemony, the shrine continued to adhere to the Nationalist Party ideology and its commemoration of Nationalist version of history. Presidents of the Republic of China, Taiwan, regardless of their political affiliation, regularly perform worship at the shrine. The ceremonies include the spring and autumn sacrifices, enshrinement of martyrs, and paying homage to the Yellow Emperor and Sun Yat-sen. The palace-style compound is a site of contested sovereignty exaggerated by China's extraordinary growth and Taiwan's transforming identity. The enshrined ancestors of the Republic of China have also found a new role as both an assertion of Taiwan's autonomy and a reflection of its dynamism in the international arena. Although the enshrinement of Republican-era heroes is part of the nation-building project under the Nationalist regime, these men also embody the struggle against imperialism (of China's past) and authoritarianism (of China's present).

Date Range: 1946 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Taipei, Taiwan

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, Taiwan

Taiwan

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Linh D. Vu, "Commemorative Contention: The Taipei Martyrs' Shrine and the Politics of Death," *Modern Asian Studies* 57, no. 1 (2023): 1–31.

– Source 2: Kirk A. Denton, *The Landscape of Historical Memory The Politics of Museums and Memorial Culture in Post-Martial Law Taiwan* (Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press, 2021), Chapter 3: Commemorating the Dead: The Taipei Martyrs Shrine and 2-28 Memorial Halls.

– Source 3: Cai Jintang. “Taiwan de zhonglie ci yu Riben de huguo shenshe jingguo shenshe zhi bijiao yanjiu [A comparative study on Taiwan’s Martyrs’ Shrine versus Japan’s Gokoku Shrine and Yasukuni Shrine]. *Shida Taiwan shixue bao* 3 (2010): 3-22.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://afrc.mnd.gov.tw/faith_martyr/

– Source 1 Description: The official website of the National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine of the Republic of China maintained by the Ministry of Defense.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/rocshrine/>

– Source 2 Description: Official Facebook page of the National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine of the Republic of China. The page is regularly updated.

– Source 3 URL: <https://law.moj.gov.tw/LawClass/LawAll.aspx?media=print&pcode=F0140008>

– Source 3 Description: Official regulations concerning who can be enshrined in the National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The shrine is located on Ching (Jing) Mountain overlooking the Keelung (Jilong) River.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: There are tall walls and guarded gates.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The shrine is located in Zhongshan District, Taipei, Taiwan. It is accessible by subway, bus, and car from the city center.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

Notes: The courtyards have camphor and pine trees, symbols of loyalty and longevity.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The shrine was constructed in the 1960s and has undergone new changes. New buildings and features have been added over time.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The features are constructed over time.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Memorial

Notes: The shrine honors over 400,000 martyrs, individually and collectively.

– Political

Notes: The shrine is a place where political rituals are held. The President and other high-ranking officials conduct ceremonies to assert the sovereignty of the Republic of China.

– Sacrificial

Notes: Sacrificial offerings are made to the martyrs.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The main material is reinforced concrete so the shrine can last a very long time.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Notes: In 1946, the Nationalist leadership renovated Taipei Shinto shrine into the National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine. The initial conversion was rather hasty, as revealed by the glaring gap between the wooden signage and the left column. An ill-fitting board was hazardously nailed across the torii (traditional Japanese gate). The inscription, 'The great spirits last for eternity' (haoqi qianqiu), referred to the spirits of the Nationalist martyrs of the War of Resistance. The layout of the National Protection Shrine and its Japanese elements, such as the stone lanterns, remained untouched. With its newfound status as the seat of the Republic of China in 1949, the island was made to adopt the ancestral revolutionaries of the Nationalist Party. Chiang Kai-shek ordered Japanese features to be removed from the National Protection Shrine, including the torii gate, and introduced many traditional Chinese architectural elements such as curved roofs and intricate lattices on three-bay gates. The properly hung sign in 1950 read 'Loyal Martyrs' Shrine' in Chiang's calligraphy. Honor guards bearing flags of the Republic of China planked the gate, which was draped with a banner, 'The Ceremony of Revolutionary Predecessor Remembrance and Spring Sacrifice for Fallen Officers and Soldiers' (Geming xianlie jinian ji chungji zhenwang jiangshi dianli). In 1958, the Nationalist government began discussing introducing more Chinese aesthetic. In meetings with representatives from the Taipei municipal government, the Ministry of Defence, and the Ministry of the Interior, a plan was made to model the new shrine after the Linggu Temple and the commemorative tower for Northern Expedition fallen officers and soldiers in Nanjing. Some expressed concern that the Taipei Martyrs' Shrine was built on the ground of a Japanese Shinto shrine, but the decision was nevertheless made to move forward. The Japanese-style stone lanterns along the walkway were replaced with Chinese-style lampposts. In 1969, the newly constructed shrine occupies an area of 52,000 square meters (about 13 acres), of which one tenth is covered by the structure and the rest is open space. The shrine undergoes regular renovation and maintenance.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: A ceremony to commemorate the Yellow Emperor, the mythological ancestor of China, is sometimes held here.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– Yes

Notes: The shrine commemorates ancestors of the Republic of China, including martyrs who died during the anti-imperial uprisings, the anti-Yuan Shikai campaigns, the Constitution Protection Movement, the Eastern Expedition, the Northern Expedition, the anti-Japanese campaigns, and the various missions to punish Communist rebels and traitors.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: In the late 1940s, Chiang Kai-shek transformed the Japanese-built National Protection Shrine (Gokoku jinja) in Taipei into a site where sacrifices were offered both to anti-imperial revolutionary martyrs and to fallen soldiers who had fought on the side of the Nationalist regime. In 1963, General He Yingqin (1890-1987), one of the most prominent politicians in the Nationalist Party, recommended renovating the Taipei Martyrs' Shrine. Ground was finally broken four years later. The shrine as we can see today was completed in 1969. Although it was estimated at 36 million yuan, the project ended up costing 53 million yuan, an expense that was shouldered by the central government, the Taiwan provincial government, and the Taipei municipal government.

↳ Specify
– Other [specify]: The Republic of China under Chinese Nationalist Party

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Notes: The shrine was created at the end of World War II.

Specify

– War/battle

Notes: The end of World War II prompted the creation of the shrine.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: the desire to commemorate the national dead and to build a nation-state.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: The shrine was built to host spirit tablets of fallen heroes.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The area is fenced by crimson walls on three sides, backs into the mountain, and overlooks the river.

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The innermost structure is the most important. Upon entering the main gate, visitors find themselves in the outer courtyard where the bell pavilion is located. A bronze statue of the martyr Lu Haodong (1868–1895), who designed the Nationalist Party flag, stands on the first floor, and a colossal bell is hung on the second floor of the pavilion. The drum tower has a status of Shi Jianru, one of the revolutionary predecessors, and the second floor has a huge drum. Bronze bells and drums are common features of religious establishments. The bell and drum in the shrine, however, are associated with awakening the people to the revolutionary cause. Passing through the mountain gate (shanmen) into the inner courtyard, the visitor then faces the great hall (dadian). On the left is the hall of civilian martyrs and on the right is the hall of military martyrs. The great hall is the most important space and is not accessible to the general public.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

Notes: Sand is used in concrete.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: Clay is used to make tiles for the roof.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Bronze

Notes: Bronze and other types of metal are used for human busts and reliefs.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Reinforced concrete, ceramic tiles

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The shrine boasts its imperial style with glazed tile roofs, painted ceilings, striking vermilion pillars, and dark marble floor. The building material, however, is reinforced concrete, instead of the traditional wood and brick. The area is fenced by crimson walls on three sides and backs into the mountain. The main entrance was adorned with a traditional Chinese architectural three-bay arch (pailou or paifang). The arch is adorned with expressions praising martyrdom: 'dying for a cause, revolting for righteousness' (chengren quyì), 'leaving a good reputation for all eternity' (wangu liufang), and 'loyalty and righteousness for a thousand years' (zhongyi qianjiu). The courtyards have camphor and pine trees, symbols of loyalty and longevity. The doorway is decorated with ornate lintels composed of four hexagonal shapes. The roofs are adorned with figures of immortals and mythical beasts. Plum blossoms, associated with the ephemerality of youth and beauty as they bloom splendidly and fade quickly, are also used as a decorative motif on the shrine roof. As in many traditional temples, the main gate is flanked by a pair of male and female lions to protect the shrine from spiritual harm.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The roofs are adorned with figures of immortals and mythical beasts in Chinese religions.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are bronze busts of martyrs.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The main gate is flanked by a pair of male and female lions

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: The doorway is decorated with ornate lintels composed of four hexagonal

shapes.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: There is plum blossom motif on the roof.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The signage 'Loyal Martyrs' Shrine' is in Chiang Kai-shek's calligraphy. He Yingqin's inscription which dedicated the shrine to national martyrs was carved on a stone tablet installed at the entrance.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: Most decorations are visible to visitors. However, casual visitors are not allowed inside the great hall where the sacrificial rites that involve state officials take place. To the left of the great hall there is a spirit tablet of 'the Yellow Emperor, the distant ancestor of the Chinese people' (Zhonghua minzu yuanzu Huang Di zhi lingwei). To the right is a portrait of Sun Yat-sen, in his role as 'the father of the nation' (guofu). At the centre of the great hall is located a sacrarium (shenkan), modeled after the one in the Shandong Temple of Confucius. In front of the sacrarium are a sacrificial offering counter and an incense burner bench. Chrysanthemums and miniature pines, both representing longevity, decorate the altar. Inside the sacrarium is placed a large spirit tablet dedicated to 'martyrs of the National Revolution' (Guomin geming lieshi zhi lingwei).

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: The hallways are adorned with bronze head busts of notable martyrs, including anti-imperial revolutionaries such as Lin Juemin (1887–1911), a participant in the Yellow Flower Hill uprising, and Qiu Jin (1875–1907), a female martyr in the late Qing. Military figures of the 1940s have also been added. For instance, General Zhang Zizhong (1891–1940) of the National Revolutionary Army was killed in a battle against the Japanese Army in Hubei. Qiu Qingquan (1902–1949) shot himself in the stomach when besieged by the Communists. Some of these martyrs are controversial figures. Liang Dunhou (1906–1949) set fire to a prison filled with Communist captives and committed suicide in Taiyuan, Shanxi.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: At the entrance of the inner courtyard are two large bronze reliefs, one that commemorates the 1911 Yellow Flower Hill Uprising and the other the 1932 First Battle of Shanghai, with captions in Chinese, English, and Japanese. The inner hallways contain two large reliefs of the 1925 Mianhu Battle, where the Huangpu Academy troops defeated Chen Jiongming, and the 1949 Battle of Guningtou, where the Nationalists succeeded in preventing the Communists from taking Kinmen (Jinmen, Quemoy) Island.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors walking along the corridors are also greeted with ten paintings commemorating (1) the founding of the Revive China Society in 1894, (2) the 1911 Yellow Flower Hill uprising, (3) the victory against Chen Jiongming in 1917, (4) the 1925 Battle of Huizhou (leading to the establishment of the Nationalist government in Guangzhou), (5) the victory against Wu Peifu (1874–1939) in 1926, (6) the victory against Sun Chuanfang (1885–1935) in 1927, (7) the Marco Polo Bridge Incident in 1937, (8) the shooting down of six Japanese airplanes by Nationalist forces on 14 August 1937, (9) Chiang Kai-shek's drafting of 100,000 people into the military in October 1944, and (10) the victory over the Japanese on 9 September 1945.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: There are a lot inscriptions to explain the historical narratives.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Memorabilia, Bell, Drum

Notes: The shrine includes documents and memorabilia of martyrs in glass cases. There are a giant bell and a giant drum. The bell and drum in the shrine are associated with awakening the people to the revolutionary cause.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: The shrine is for the worship of martyrs. But it also serves as a funeral hall for political leaders. For example, the shrine served as a funeral hall for Chiang Kai-shek's son and successor, Chiang Ching-kuo (1910–1988), who died in 1988. His open casket lay in state at the Martyrs' Shrine for a week before being transferred to his private temple in Cihu. During this time, the shrine was decorated with funerary yellow flowers, as well as crosses, for Chiang was a Baptist. Nuns and monks of various sects performed rituals. Groups of students, farmers, workers, and soldiers—people from all walks of life—and foreign dignitaries came to pay homage. Chiang's

family members were in attendance, returning bows to mourners following the traditional practice. Top leaders of the government and the National Party kept vigil as a sign of both loyalty and filiality.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Notes: The shrine is a place of martyr worship. The list of martyrs includes Zou Rong (1885–1905), who argued for the racial differences between Chinese and Manchu people and advocated a violent end to the Qing rule. The register of Republican martyrs included several assassins who targeted Qing officials. Shi Jianru (1879–1900), a member of the Revive China Society (Xingzhong hui), was beheaded for plotting a bomb attack on the governor of Guangdong in 1900. A member of the Restoration Society (Guangfu hui) and Northern Assassination Corps (Beifang ansha tuan), Wu Yue (1878–1905), died while attempting a suicide-bomb attack on Qing commissioners. Xu Xilin (1873–1907) was publicly dismembered after having assassinated a Manchu bannerman. Yang Zhuolin (1876–1907) was executed for attempting to murder a Manchu governor-general. Wen Shengcai (1870–1911) was beheaded for killing a Manchu general with a pistol. Peng Jiazhen (1888–1912) perished by his own explosives while trying to assassinate a Manchu commander. Some of the most celebrated martyrs were from the Yellow Flower Hill (Huanghuagang) uprising on 27 April 1911 (29 March in the lunar calendar). A group of local gentry, businessmen, overseas students, and secret society members, some of whom belonged to Sun Yat-sen's Revolutionary Alliance (Tongmenghui), staged an armed revolt in Guangzhou. Because their plan had been leaked to the authorities, the imperial troops crushed the uprising. The new shrine completed in 1969 also accepted new inhabitants. In March 1970, Chiang Kai-shek approved the enshrinement of martyrs from the island's past, such as Lo Fu-hsing (1886–1914), Yu Qingfang (1879–1916), Mona Ludao (1880–1930), and Hanaoka Ichirō (?–1930). These martyrs were Hakka Chinese, overseas Chinese, and aborigines who resisted Japanese colonial rule (1895–1945). The son of a Hakka Chinese businessman and a local woman in Batavia (the capital of the Dutch East Indies), Lo Fu-hsing was inspired by Sun Yat-sen's ideology to revolt against the Japanese authorities in the 1913 Miaoli Incident. Yu Qingfang led the 1915 Ta-pa-ni Incident, a large-scale millenarian armed revolt against Japanese rule. Mona Ludao led some 300 indigenes in raiding the government arsenals and attacked Japanese nationals in the 1930 Musha (Wushe) Incident. Hanaoka Ichirō, an aborigine educated in the Japanese colonial order, committed seppuku (ritual suicide by disembowelment) when the authorities crushed the rebellion. These incidents led to the persecution of thousands of people on the island. These martyrs were portrayed as loyal citizens of the Republic of China who had sought to 'recover' the motherland from Japanese invaders. The shrine continues to accept new residents. For example, in August 2014, an enshrinement ceremony was organized for the fallen Chinese soldiers in the Burma campaign of 1942–1943. The wooden tablet carrying the souls of over 56,000 Chinese expeditionary soldiers was transported from Myitkyina to Taipei by air and placed on the altar by the ceremonial guards. During the autumn sacrifice of 2014, President Ma Ying-jeou performed a lengthy service to honor the expeditionary soldiers from Burma after their spirits returned 'home.' In March 2019, two officers who died during the Second Sino-Japanese War were enshrined. Lieutenant-Colonel Bi Fuchang, a captain in the intelligence attachment of the Third Division of the Tenth Army, was killed in 1943 while leading an espionage unit during the battle against the Japanese Army in Deshan, Hunan. Major Liu Chengxun led an artillery battery in the Nanjing-Jiangning Fortress Command and

perished during the battle in Tongshan, Jiangsu, in 1938. Asserting Taiwan's version of the War of Resistance against Japan is crucial to the island's fight for autonomy, especially at a time when the Chinese Communist Party has been undervaluing the Nationalist regime's war effort. Another notable case has been of Zhao Zhongrong (1905–1951), an army commander who was arrested during the Chinese Civil War and subsequently executed in Beijing. After his daughter, Zhao Anna, spent two decades collecting evidence of his martyrdom and petitioning to the Executive Yuan, Zhao Zhongrong was enshrined in 2018.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: The main commemorative mode is the offerings of sacrifices to spirit tablets. This feature is based on the belief that the spirits of the dead inhabit spirit tablets and receive sacrificial offerings made to them. Spirit tablets used in making offerings to the dead were popularized and standardized by the Song Neo-Confucian Zhu Xi (1130–1200). The shrine also commemorates Sun Yat-sen as the founding father of the Chinese nation.

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: The spirits of martyrs are conjured up to enjoy the sacrificial offerings, but this is more of a metaphorical expression rather than an indication of actual communication with human spirits.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: The inaugural president makes offerings to the Yellow Emperor, a mytho-historical ruler. He is also considered a deity in Chinese religion.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: But there is a spirit tablet of 'the Yellow Emperor.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Notes: There are public sacrifices (gongji), which are public commemorative rituals. Sacrifices are material goods such as incense, flowers, etc.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: There are public sacrifices (gongji), which are public commemorative rituals. Sacrifices are material goods such as fruits, incense, flowers, etc.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Yellow flower wreaths

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

Notes: The general public and visitors from all over the world visit the shrine, but not to participate in the ritual of worship. Families of martyrs may pay homage to their deceased.

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: President, Vice President, Heads of the Five Yuans, Military Officers

Notes: New ROC presidents pay their respects to the Yellow Emperor on April 5 and to Sun Yat-sen at their inauguration. More importantly, during the spring and autumn sacrifices, the President, assisted by the head of the Five Yuans (the Executive, Legislative, Judicial, Examination, and Control branches of the government), presided over the ceremony. The spring sacrifice was set for 29 March, the anniversary of the Yellow Flower Hill uprising (also chosen as Youth Day) and the autumn sacrifice for 3 September—the anniversary of the end of World War II (also chosen as Armed Forces Day). The ceremony began at ten o'clock and lasted half an hour, during which time participants played music, presented flowers, read elegies, and made three bows. During the ceremony, the martyrs' spirits were conjured up to 'partake in the offerings' (shang xiang). Each year, the Presidential Office staff drafted a new elegy with content that emphasized the transcendental nature of martyrdom. There are also ceremonies of enshrinement. During the Cold War, a stop at the Loyal Martyrs' Shrine was an essential part of the itineraries of visiting foreign officials from such countries as Bolivia, Dahomey (Benin), the Gambia, Iran, Italy, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Panama, Paraguay, the Philippines, South Vietnam, Spain, and the United States. Abiding by the one-China policy, the Nationalist Party strove to reinforce its claim of sovereignty over the Communist Party by having foreign diplomats to 'lay a flower wreath and pay homage' (xianhua zhijing) to the Republican martyrs. According to the National Revolutionary Martyrs' Shrine Wreath-Laying Ceremony Guidelines in effect from 1966 to 1975, foreign dignitaries were met at the outer courtyard and escorted by honor guards. The visitors climbed up some stairs into the inner courtyard and entered the great hall. Once inside, the visiting chief of state took his place at the centre facing the martyrs' altar. An aid handed him a yellow flower wreath, which the official held aloft for a moment before handing it back to be placed on the altar. Taps were sounded while all the attendees stood in silence. After the ceremony concluded, the visitors were escorted back to the outer courtyard. The visit lasted fifteen minutes.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Other

– Other [specify]: Fresh flowers and incense sticks are always present.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: People do not make pilgrimages to this shrine, but many visit as tourists. They come in tour buses to watch the honor guards perform their changing of the guard rituals. The rituals include impressive gun toting and goose stepping techniques. Families of martyrs also visit and pay homage to the spirit tablets of the deceased.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The inaugural ceremony in March 1969 included over two thousand participants. The minister of the interior officiated at the civilian martyrs' shrine with the assistance of the head of the Five Yuans. The minister of defence officiated for the military martyrs with the assistance of the chief of staff and the commander-in-chief of five branches of the armed forces. Representatives from government offices and the Nationalist Party, students, and martyrs'

children also attended. During funerals of top leaders, thousands of people participated.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: During the spring and autumn sacrifices, the number of participants is likely around a hundred, mostly involved high-ranking government officials. Enshrinement ceremonies of martyrs are of the same scale, but include families of the dead.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Hundreds and thousands

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: On average, once a month.

Notes: Besides the spring and autumn sacrifices, there are enshrinement ceremonies and other anniversaries throughout the year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The shrine is maintained by the Ministry of Defense.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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